

Global temperature trends in the satellite era: evidence from MODIS LST and long-record weather stations

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Abstract

This paper examines recent land surface temperature (LST) trends using globally gridded satellite data and benchmarks them against long-record observations from land-based weather stations. Drawing on four MODIS Terra and Aqua Collection 6.1 LST products at 0.05° resolution, the analysis uses over 160 billion quality-filtered daily observations to estimate grid-wise trends and global anomaly trends with robust inference.

Over 2001–2019 (Terra) and 2003–2020 (Aqua), unified global temperature trends range from about 0.02 to 0.04 °C per year, with nighttime warming more than daytime warming. Comparable fixed-effects estimates from 992 long-record GHCN stations show positive but generally smaller warming rates over the same periods. Extending the station record back to the late nineteenth century reveals that many of the strongest 18 and 19-year warming episodes occurred before 1940, when cumulative anthropogenic CO₂ emissions were around one-tenth of what they are today. Together, the satellite-based and station-based analyses provide an empirical reference for situating recent global temperature trends within both the satellite era and the longer instrumental record. Policy assessment of climate interventions should account for the existence of higher historical warming episodes at vastly lower anthropogenic CO₂ emissions.

Keywords: Global warming; Land Surface Temperature; MODIS; Temperature trends; Climate change; Climate policy

JEL codes: Q54; Q56; C23; C55

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1 Introduction

Long-term temperature trends are of interest to policymakers, researchers, and international organisations. Rising trends are widely attributed to anthropogenic greenhouse gases, especially carbon dioxide (CO₂)¹, and have prompted policy measures aimed at reducing carbon emissions to limit further global warming. A large body of work has constructed global near-surface temperature datasets by merging land-station air temperatures with sea-surface temperature measurements. Prominent examples include the GISS analysis of global surface temperature change (Hansen et al., 2010) and the HadCRUT series (Morice et al., 2021). These products supply monthly, globally gridded air-temperature anomalies from the mid-nineteenth century onward and underpin most assessments of historical warming. In contrast, the present study focuses on satellite-retrieved land surface temperature (LST) over the early twenty-first century and compares these retrievals directly with long-record station data, rather than contributing another global air-temperature synthesis.

Public and policy discourse frequently portrays recent decades as uniquely warm, attributing multi-decadal temperature trends primarily to rising anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. For example, the World Meteorological Organization (WMO), in its 23 March 2026 press release² accompanying the State of the Global Climate 2025 report, stated that the years 2015–2025 were “the hottest 11 years on record”. This view was echoed in the same release by the Secretary-General of the United Nations. Similarly, Berkeley Earth, a US-based non-profit engaged in climate research, reported³ that “the last 11 years have included all 11 of the warmest years observed in the instrumental record”. In a policy statement entitled “State of Climate and Nature” delivered in the House of Commons⁴, the UK Secretary of State for Energy Security and Net Zero likewise emphasised that “*Only by bringing down carbon emissions, protecting nature, and working internationally can we deliver energy security today, and climate security for future generations.*”

In contrast to these long historical air-temperature datasets, satellite remote sensing now provides high-resolution global LST records from the early 2000s onward. These products, however, have a shorter temporal span and different measurement characteristics than traditional air-temperature records from weather stations. This raises two questions central to this study: (i) what do satellite LST data indicate about recent land-temperature trends,

¹In public discourse, the terms ‘carbon’ and ‘carbon dioxide’ are often used interchangeably, despite referring to different chemical entities.

²<https://wmo.int/news/media-centre/earths-climate-swings-increasingly-out-of-balance> (accessed 1 April 2026)

³<https://berkeleyearth.org/global-temperature-report-for-2025/> (accessed 1 April 2026)

⁴<https://questions-statements.parliament.uk/written-statements/detail/2025-07-14/hcws817> (accessed 1 April 2026)

and (ii) how do these trends compare with long-record station observations?

By integrating MODIS LST with long-record Global Historical Climatology Network (GHCN) stations, this study pursues two primary objectives. First, it quantifies recent land-temperature trends using high-resolution satellite data. Second, it benchmarks these satellite-era trends against historical multi-decadal warming episodes recorded by in-situ stations, comparing them both over matching recent periods and over earlier 18- or 19-year windows extending back to the late nineteenth century. The analysis draws on 992 GHCN stations with data from at least 1900 (Bhatta, 2025), employs station fixed effects and seasonal controls, and situates recent warming within the broader spectrum of historical multi-decadal temperature changes.

Together, these datasets provide a coherent empirical basis for understanding land-temperature evolution in both the satellite era and the longer instrumental record.

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows: Section 2 describes the data; section 3 discusses the methods, Section 4 presents the findings, and Section 5 offers concluding remarks.

2 Data

Daily land surface temperature (LST) observations were obtained from the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) instruments aboard NASA's Terra and Aqua satellites. Specifically, the MOD11C1 (Terra)⁵ and MYD11C1 (Aqua)⁶ Collection 6.1 daily LST products were used (Wan et al., 2021) providing global coverage at 0.05° spatial resolution (approximately 5.6 km at the equator) on a Climate Modeling Grid (CMG). Each satellite retrieves LST at two equatorial overpass times: approximately 10:30 AM and 10:30 PM local solar time for Terra, and approximately 1:30 PM and 1:30 AM for Aqua. These four overpass times yield four distinct LST variables: Terra daytime, Terra nighttime, Aqua daytime, and Aqua nighttime.

2.1 Temporal Coverage and Orbital Stability

The temporal coverage for each variable was strictly constrained to complete calendar years within periods of stable orbital geometry. Terra was placed into a controlled Sun-synchronous orbit maintaining a 10:30 AM equatorial crossing time from early 2000. However,

⁵<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/catalog/lpcloud-mod11c1-061>

⁶<https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/data/catalog/lpcloud-myd11c1-061>

NASA suspended orbit maintenance manoeuvres for Terra in February 2020, after which the equatorial crossing time began drifting systematically earlier. This drift introduces a progressive bias in daytime LST observations attributable to changes in local solar illumination rather than true surface temperature trends. Accordingly, Terra data were restricted to the 19 full calendar years from January 2001 through December 2019.

Aqua's last orbit maintenance manoeuvre was performed in March 2021, after which its equatorial crossing time began drifting later. Aqua data were therefore restricted to the 18 full calendar years from January 2003 through December 2020. Constraining the data to complete calendar years ensures that the seasonal cycle is balanced at the boundaries of the time series. These orbit-drift cutoffs were applied uniformly across both daytime and nighttime variables.

2.2 Spatial Coverage and Observation Density

At 0.05° spatial resolution, the global CMG grid comprises 25.9 million cells (3600×7200). Because oceans lack valid LST retrievals, only land pixels are retained, yielding approximately 8.7 million grid cells for each of the four variables (about 33% of the Earth's surface). For stricter data quality, we also apply a threshold of at least 50% data availability later.

To ensure adequate temporal sampling for trend estimation, only land pixels with at least 1000 valid observations over the analysis period are included. This threshold balances spatial coverage with sufficient temporal density to support reliable regression estimates.

2.3 Quality Control Procedures

Raw MODIS LST retrievals were subjected to a multi-stage quality control procedure applied at the point of extraction from the original files. First, pixels flagged with the sensor fill value (default: -28,672 in raw integer units) were set to missing, removing scenes for which no retrieval was attempted, including open ocean, polar night, and sensor gaps. Second, any raw digital number falling outside the product-documented valid range (encoded in the HDF metadata attributes) was discarded, guarding against saturated or corrupted pixel values. Third, the mandatory quality assurance (QA) flags embedded in the QC_Day and QC_Night science data sets were examined: only pixels whose two least-significant QA bits (bits 0–1) equalled 00 (LST produced, good quality) or 01 (LST produced, other quality) were retained; pixels with values 10 (cloud-contaminated) or 11 (retrieval failed for other reasons) were set to missing. These three checks were applied independently to daytime and night-time retrievals from both Terra and Aqua before any data were written to the long-term archive,

ensuring that cloud contamination did not make its way into downstream analysis.

2.4 Observation Totals

The total number of valid daily observations available for each dataset is approximately 40 billion, as summarised in Table 1. Across the four variables, the analysis draws on more than 160 billion quality-filtered LST observations, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Observations used in the study from each of the 4 datasets

Dataset	Start year	End year	Valid grids (>1000 obs)	Valid obs (billions)	Avg obs per grid
Terra day	2001	2019	8,823,570	41.88	4746
Terra night	2001	2019	8,699,627	42.54	4890
Aqua day	2003	2020	8,836,925	38.69	4378
Aqua night	2003	2020	8,678,883	39.30	4528

2.5 Monthly Extremes and Distributional Characteristics

To provide a high-level overview of the data, monthly maximum and minimum LST values were computed for each product, along with the corresponding grid locations (latitude and longitude rounded to two decimals). For brevity, we show the maximum and minimum only for the Terra night dataset (Table 2). To further characterise the distribution of LST values, Table 3 reports monthly percentiles for the Terra nighttime dataset.

Table 2: Maximum and minimum temperature with location for each month (Terra night)

Month	Min LST	Min Lat	Min Lon	Min Date	Max LST	Max Lat	Max Lon	Max Date	Mean LST
1	-76.2	67.38	-41.23	22/01/2007	64.5	-16.88	-62.03	19/01/2008	-16.99
2	-74.4	62.53	-43.98	18/02/2011	60.4	-26.23	140.23	24/02/2015	-19.93
3	-82.8	-81.93	73.93	28/03/2013	66.6	25.63	55.93	22/03/2004	-20.47
4	-86.4	-78.58	92.83	22/04/2010	66.1	22.38	12.33	24/04/2006	-18.3
5	-90.4	-79.63	46.18	21/05/2013	65.5	26.93	57.03	08/05/2012	-14.78
6	-108.3	5.98	-76.08	15/06/2005	66.4	20.38	48.68	30/06/2019	-11.96
7	-95.2	-79.03	43.98	09/07/2001	66.7	23.58	55.43	17/07/2003	-11.35
8	-99.0	-72.28	-60.83	24/08/2019	66.2	19.98	50.13	27/08/2008	-12.04

Month	Min LST	Min Lat	Min Lon	Min Date	Max LST	Max Lat	Max Lon	Max Date	Mean LST
9	-97.3	-69.53	-62.28	07/09/2017	66.7	64.88	-16.88	24/09/2014	-14.01
10	-89.0	-80.53	52.68	05/10/2007	65.4	64.88	-16.93	19/10/2014	-15.34
11	-75.9	-72.03	105.63	02/11/2015	64.0	22.38	24.83	29/11/2013	-15.96
12	-73.4	72.68	-38.93	07/12/2011	65.8	-1.38	29.33	02/12/2011	-15.76

Table 3: Temperature percentiles (deg C) for each month (Terra night)

Month	N (billion)	Min	P10	P25	P50	P75	P90	Mean	Max
1	3.64	-76.17	-38.09	-32.07	-23.11	-2.61	16.17	-16.99	64.53
2	3.28	-74.35	-44.95	-37.79	-26.07	-2.39	17.69	-19.93	60.37
3	3.62	-82.77	-54.67	-42.05	-23.73	2.07	19.01	-20.47	66.63
4	3.56	-86.39	-58.99	-44.35	-15.55	6.69	19.81	-18.3	66.13
5	3.67	-90.37	-59.91	-45.25	-5.83	10.79	20.93	-14.78	65.47
6	3.41	-108.31	-61.41	-47.25	2.49	14.27	22.53	-11.96	66.43
7	3.59	-95.15	-63.29	-49.59	5.85	16.01	23.21	-11.35	66.73
8	3.64	-98.99	-62.95	-49.65	3.89	15.25	22.95	-12.04	66.19
9	3.54	-97.29	-62.31	-48.21	-1.59	13.09	22.29	-14.01	66.65
10	3.55	-88.99	-54.61	-41.67	-10.99	9.59	20.97	-15.34	65.41
11	3.48	-75.85	-42.79	-35.07	-20.29	3.95	18.35	-15.96	63.99
12	3.54	-73.39	-36.99	-30.79	-21.55	-0.87	16.47	-15.76	65.75

For minimum LST, the land temperature of -108.3 degrees centigrade in June in a place in South America (Colombia) looks implausible. Hence, for further analysis, a filter was imposed on all retained retrievals prior to seasonal de-meaning. Any pixel-day observation falling outside the range $[-99.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}, +90\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}]$ for daytime variables and $[-99.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}, +75\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}]$ for nighttime variables was set to missing. The lower bound is in alignment with the coldest land surface temperature ever recorded by satellite, as measured over the East Antarctic Plateau (Scambos et al., 2018), and is sufficiently conservative to retain all genuine polar retrievals while excluding physically impossible values such as those occasionally produced by retrieval failures in tropical and mid-latitude regions. The upper bounds reflect a margin above the highest land surface temperatures reliably documented in hyper-arid environments such as the Lut Desert (Azarderakhsh et al., 2020).

3 Methods

This section describes the procedures used to estimate long-term land-surface temperature (LST) trends from the MODIS datasets and to construct unified global warming rates. The analysis proceeds in two stages: (i) seasonal adjustment and anomaly construction, leading to grid-level trend estimation, and (ii) global trend estimation using area-weighted anomalies and an alternative aggregation of pixel-level slopes using area weights.

3.1 Grid-wise Temperature Trends

Long-term LST trends were estimated for each land pixel using ordinary least squares (OLS) linear regression of the daily LST time series against a sequential time index. To control for the seasonal variance in daily temperature data without explicitly imposing 11 monthly dummy variables in the regression matrix, the seasonal cycle was extracted using the Frisch-Waugh-Lovell (FWL) approach (Lovell, 1963). Prior to regression, a pixel-wise monthly climatology (the historical mean for each of the 12 calendar months) was computed and subtracted from the daily observations of each grid. This within-transformation demeans the data, transforming the raw temperatures into daily anomalies.

OLS slope estimates and residual sums of squares were then calculated directly from the seasonally-adjusted observations. Because the FWL de-meaning implicitly estimates 11 monthly parameters, the degrees of freedom for the residual variance were appropriately adjusted from $N - 2$ to $N - 13$. Two-tailed p-values were computed using these adjusted degrees of freedom to ensure valid statistical inference. Slope estimates were converted from Centigrade per day to Centigrade per year by multiplying by 365.25.

3.2 Unified Global Slope with Grid Fixed Effects

To estimate a single unified global warming rate, analogous to a panel regression with two-way fixed effects for space and season, an area-weighted global LST anomaly series was constructed. The data were first deseasonalized globally via the FWL monthly de-meaning procedure described above. Next, a spatial fixed effect was removed by computing the temporal mean for each land pixel over the full analysis period and subtracting it from the deseasonalized daily observations, thereby isolating pure within-pixel weather and climate anomalies. These anomalies were then aggregated into a daily global mean series using cosine-of-latitude area weights.

This approach directly averages the local warming rates while correctly accounting for

the convergence of meridians at higher latitudes: because equal-angle latitude–longitude grid cells become progressively smaller toward the poles, area weighting ensures that each cell contributes in proportion to the physical land area it represents ⁷. Without such weighting, high-latitude cells would be overrepresented in the global average.

The unified global slope was estimated by regressing this one-dimensional global anomaly series against a daily time index using ordinary least squares (OLS). Newey–West heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation consistent (HAC) standard errors (Newey and West, 1987) were computed with a maximum lag of 365 days to account for the persistence of synoptic weather systems in the anomaly residuals. The slope estimate was multiplied by 365.25 to express it in °C per year, and 95% confidence intervals were constructed as $\pm 1.96 \times$ the HAC standard error. This specification controls for seasonal cycles and cross-sectional spatial heterogeneity, yielding a single, robustly estimated global temperature trend.

As an alternative specification to the global anomaly regression, we also computed an area-weighted mean of the pixel-level linear trends. For each of the four MODIS LST variables (Terra day/night, Aqua day/night), ordinary least-squares (OLS) slopes were first estimated independently as discussed earlier. The resulting slope field (in C /year) was then aggregated into a single unified estimate by computing the area-weighted mean across all valid pixels. Area weights were calculated as discussed earlier and ensures that each pixel contributes in proportion to the actual land surface area it represents. This approach directly averages the local warming rates while correctly accounting for the convergence of meridians at higher latitudes, and provides a complementary summary measure of the overall land-surface temperature trend.

4 Findings

This section presents the empirical results from the MODIS land-surface temperature (LST) datasets and the long-record Global Historical Climatology Network (GHCN) stations. We begin with pixel-level trend estimates, then report unified global warming rates, and finally compare satellite-era trends with both contemporary and historical station-based warming episodes.

Given the vast number of grid cells with individual trends over the study period, we first present the grid-wise trend visualization for each of the data variables, before presenting the global unified slope.

⁷For instance, a grid cell at latitude -29.375° and longitude 141.825° has an area $\sim 13\%$ smaller than an equatorial grid cell at the same longitude [$1 - \cos(29.375^\circ) = 12.8\%$]. See Stewart (2015; Ch 15) for a formal mathematical treatment of spherical coordinates and area elements.

4.1 Grid-wise slopes

Warming trends (positive slope with statistical significance) are shown in red dots and cooling trends are shown in blue dots while statistically insignificant slopes are shown in black. Grids with white dots denote unavailability of data.

Figure 1: Grid-wise temperature trends based on Terra daytime (10:30 am) observations

Morning temperatures (as observed through Terra day at approximately 10:30 am) show generally warming trends, as exhibited in Figure 1. The northern regions exhibit relatively stronger warming trends (as denoted by dark red patches) whereas the northern US and India are dotted with blue markers denoting cooling trends. Greenland largely does not exhibit statistically significant temperature trends, as denoted by black patches.

Afternoon temperatures also follow a largely similar pattern as shown in Figure 2. The northern US and southern Canada continue to show cooling trends along with India; and northern Russia remains on the warming trajectory while a large portion of antarctica does not exhibit statistically significant trends.

Temperature trends from nighttime observations are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4 for Terra night (10:30 pm) and Aqua nighttime (1:30 am) temperature trends respectively.

A visual assessment of the charts above shows that warming trends are more dominant during nighttime than during daytime. This is exhibited numerically in Table 4.

Land Surface Temperature - MODIS Aqua (Daytime) (2003-2020)
Gridwise temperature trend | $p < 0.05$ | black = not statistically significant

Figure 2: Grid-wise temperature trends based on Aqua daytime (1:30 pm) observations

Land Surface Temperature - MODIS Terra (Nighttime) (2001-2019)
Gridwise temperature trend | $p < 0.05$ | black = not statistically significant

Figure 3: Grid-wise temperature trends - Terra nighttime (10:30 pm) observations

Land Surface Temperature - MODIS Aqua (Nighttime) (2003–2020)
 Gridwise temperature trend | $p < 0.05$ | black = not statistically significant

Figure 4: Grid-wise temperature trends - Aqua nighttime (1:30 am) observations

Table 4: Summary statistics of grid-wise trends

Dataset	Min slope (C/yr)	Median slope (C/yr)	Mean slope (C/yr)	Max slope (C/yr)	Significant warming grids (p<0.05)	Significant cooling grids (p<0.05)	Grids with significant slopes
Terra day	-1.2814	0.0154	0.0198	1.3002	3,559,683	1,333,510	55.5%
Terra night	-0.5388	0.0281	0.0288	0.6268	4,822,387	551,635	61.8%
Aqua day	-1.4642	0.0255	0.0325	1.3220	4,049,612	760,402	54.4%
Aqua night	-0.5872	0.0332	0.0381	0.7408	5,231,011	239,287	63.0%

Median as well as average slopes for all four variables are positive (warming). Warming trend during nighttime is more widespread at 1:30 am local time with 5.2 million of the land grids exhibiting the warming trends at that time. The median slopes range from 0.015 (Terra day) to 0.0332 (Aqua night) degree centigrade per year; and the simple average mean slopes follow a similar pattern, as shown in Table 4.

To ensure these spatial patterns are not due to sparse temporal sampling, a strict robustness check was performed. Re-estimating the trends using only grids with at least 50%

data availability yields highly consistent results, though it inherently omits large areas in northern South America and central Africa, as shown in Appendix I.

4.2 Unified slopes

Unified slopes for all the four variables are presented in Table 5. Global warming trends for the shown duration range from 0.0217 to 0.0386 centigrade per year, based on the deseasonalized data and all estimates are statistically significant at 95% confidence level. The alternative global slopes, which are based on the OLS slopes of individual grids and are weighted by area coverage (as discussed earlier) are shown in the rightmost column of Table 5.

Table 5: Unified slopes

Dataset	Years	slope	p_value	CI_lower	CI_upper	Area-wt slope
Terra day	2001-2019	0.0217	0.0013	0.0085	0.0350	0.0227
Terra night	2001-2019	0.0330	0.0000	0.0224	0.0436	0.0338
Aqua day	2003-2020	0.0316	0.0000	0.0188	0.0443	0.0313
Aqua night	2003-2020	0.0386	0.0000	0.0263	0.0510	0.0387

4.3 Comparison with land-based weather stations

It would be ideal if satellite LST had a longer historical record. Since we do not have such historical record, we compare the satellite-based temperature observations with land-based temperature observations. For this purpose, we take the GHCN daily temperature data and compare the temperature trend along similar time dimension as Terra (2001-2019) and Aqua (2003-2020). From GHCN, we take only those stations where data is available from at least 1900 so that we have a history of at least 120 years. This is useful if we want to compare the satellite data to pre-2000 and historical temperature trends (as we will do in the following section). These selection criteria provide data from 992 weather stations from 29 countries, as depicted in Figure 5.

After the cleaning process, the final sample for analysis has 42,456,992 records showing both minimum and maximum temperatures. We calculate the daily average as the simple average of maximum and minimum temperatures for all stations and employ a within-station variation (station fixed effect) model to find the overall temperature trends for daily maximum (TMAX), minimum (TMIN) and average temperature (TAVG). We also control for seasonal

Figure 5: Land-based 992 weather stations

variations and urban heat island (UHI) effect, as discussed in more detail in Bhatta (2025). The temperature trends for the comparable periods but from land-based stations are shown in Table 6. The rightmost column of Table 6 reports cumulative anthropogenic CO₂ emissions⁸ over the corresponding periods, providing context for the magnitude of recent warming relative to historical emissions.

Table 6: Temperature trends along comparable periods based on land-based stations

Temp	Period	Change/year	Obs	Stations	P-value	Cum CO2
TAVG	2003-2020	0.020	5,926,681	988	0.0002	600.8
TMIN	2003-2020	0.025	5,926,681	988	0.0000	600.8
TMAX	2003-2020	0.015	5,926,681	988	0.0194	600.8
TAVG	2001-2019	0.007	6,293,294	988	0.1788	617.6
TMIN	2001-2019	0.014	6,293,294	988	0.0038	617.6
TMAX	2001-2019	0.001	6,293,294	988	0.8998	617.6

For Aqua data (2003-2020), the temperature rate of change per year is 0.025 for TMIN which is lower than what is observed based on LST.

Similarly, for Terra data (2001-2019), the only statistically significant temperature rate of

⁸Data on annual human CO₂ emissions is from Our World In Data.

change per year is 0.014 for TMIN which is also lower than what is observed based on LST. These disparities could be due to differences in data source and coverage. While the common theme is that both sets of data show a warming trend, the trend shown by land-based stations seems to be on the lower side.

4.4 Comparison with pre-2000 temperature trends

To place recent satellite-era warming in historical context, we examine all 18-year and 19-year warming episodes in the long-record GHCN station data. Table 7 and Table 8 list the five strongest warming periods for each window length, based on trends in daily average temperature (TAVG). For example, the periods 1883–1900, 1916–1933, and 1917–1934 exhibit warming rates between 0.050 and 0.060 °C

Table 7: Historical temperature trends over 18-year periods (TAVG)

Period	Change/year	Obs	Stations	P-value	Cum CO2
1883-1900	0.054	2,069,205	989	0.0000	24.6
1916-1933	0.050	5,476,385	952	0.0000	64.6
1917-1934	0.060	5,493,855	951	0.0000	64.9
1922-1939	0.048	5,633,794	960	0.0000	69.3
2007-2024	0.058	5,776,253	991	0.0000	635.4

Table 8: Historical temperature trends over 19-year periods (TAVG)

Period	Change/year	Obs	Stations	P-value	Cum CO2
1882-1900	0.047	2,091,241	989	0.0000	25.5
1883-1901	0.043	2,341,104	990	0.0000	26.6
1915-1933	0.048	5,777,398	958	0.0000	67.8
1916-1934	0.060	5,795,238	952	0.0000	68.3
1917-1935	0.050	5,814,541	953	0.0000	68.7

Out of 10 observations, nine periods with the highest rate of warming occurred at least 80 years ago. All the top nine historical periods shown in Table 7 and Table 8 witnessed anthropogenic CO2 emissions that were a fraction of the more recent period (at least 1/9).

Taken together, the grid-level MODIS trends, unified global warming rates, and station-based comparisons provide a coherent empirical picture of land-temperature evolution

in the satellite era. The MODIS datasets reveal warming across global land areas, particularly at night, with global trends between 0.02 and 0.04 °C per year. Station-based records confirm positive warming over the same periods, albeit at somewhat lower rates recently but at higher rates more than 80 years ago. These results offer a compact empirical reference for understanding global temperature trends in both contemporary and historical context.

5 Concluding Remarks

This study provides a comprehensive assessment of recent land-surface temperature (LST) trends using more than 160 billion quality-filtered daily observations from four MODIS Collection 6.1 products, benchmarked against long-record temperature measurements from 992 GHCN weather stations. Across all MODIS variables, global land areas exhibit statistically significant warming over the satellite era, with unified global trends ranging from 0.02 to 0.04 °C per year. Warming is more pronounced and spatially widespread at night than during the day. These patterns are robust across both grid-level regressions and area-weighted global anomaly estimates.

Comparisons with land-based weather stations show that station-derived recent warming rates over the same periods are positive but generally smaller than those retrieved from MODIS LST. Differences in magnitude between satellite-retrieved LST and station-based air temperatures are possibly due to differences in measurement height, surface–atmosphere coupling, and spatial representativeness. Taken together, the two datasets provide complementary perspectives on recent global temperature evolution.

Extending the station record back to the late nineteenth century reveals that most of the strongest 18- and 19-year warming episodes occurred before 1950, when cumulative anthropogenic CO₂ emissions were less than one-ninth of what they are today.

The contribution of this study is primarily empirical: it offers a large-scale, internally consistent analysis of MODIS LST trends; a direct comparison with long-record station data; and a historical benchmark for interpreting recent warming episodes. The findings underscore the value of maintaining long-term satellite observations and high-quality station networks, both of which are essential for monitoring land-temperature change and for contextualising short-period trends within the broader instrumental record.

Future work could extend this analysis using forthcoming MODIS products, integrate LST trends with reanalysis or land-surface model outputs, or examine regional drivers of the observed diurnal asymmetry in warming. Continued development of harmonised satellite and in-situ datasets will further strengthen our ability to track, interpret, and understand

land-temperature evolution in a changing climate.

5.1 Limitations

First, the MODIS LST record spans only two decades and measures radiative land-surface skin temperature rather than near-surface air temperature, cannot document longer historical trends, and excludes ocean temperatures. The analysis period reflects data availability and orbital stability constraints rather than climate science design choices. Second, the GHCN station sample (records from ≥ 1900) may not fully represent the global land network and may retain residual inhomogeneities or urbanisation effects despite applied controls; urban heat island effects likely influence station data more than satellite LST. Third, comparing satellite LST with weather-station air temperatures yields complementary but not directly comparable measures, highlighting the need for long-term, harmonised satellite-station datasets. Fourth, the choice of 18- and 19-year windows remains arbitrary; optimal windows for identifying long-term climate trends remain an open question for future research. Finally, the analysis is descriptive. It quantifies trends and contextualises them against cumulative CO₂ but does not attempt formal attribution.

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Appendices

Land Surface Temperature - MODIS Terra (Daytime) (2001-2019)
Gridwise temperature trend | $p < 0.05$ | black = not statistically significant

Appendix I: Temperature trends using grids with at least 50% non-missing data